

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Catalogue of Solutions

Deliverable 6.3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	D6.3 – Catalogue of Solutions
Work Package	WP6 – Acceptance building and exploitation of innovation packages
Dissemination Level	Public
Author(s)	<p>University of Antwerp, Belgium: Rosaly Severijns, Jan Cools, Laura Enthoven, Haoran Yu</p> <p>Guadeloupe, France: Pauline Guérécheau-Desvignes, Marianna Martel, Florent Passalacqua, Lynn Michaux, Filiep Dewitte</p> <p>Oristano, Italy: Alessio Satta, Manuela Puddu, Francesca Etzi, Piera Pala, Emanuele Tiddia</p> <p>Egaleo, Greece: Stelios Karozis, Dimitris Tzempelikos, Evrydiki Pavlidi, Thanasis Sfetsos, Ioannis Zarikos,</p> <p>Lappeenranta, Finland: Sanna Varis, Laura Ratilainen, Satu-Pia Reinikainen, Tuomas Sihvonen, Liuliu Du-Ikonen</p> <p>Galicia, Spain: Andrea Ogando Vidal, Carlos Rodriguez Garcia, Xose Anton Alvarez Salgado, Silvia Piedracoba, Isabel Fuentes, Cristian Simoes Fernández, Ignacio González Liaño, Eva Méndez, Christian Moreira, Silvia Torres López, Lucía Fraga, Amaya Soto Rey, Clara Almécija, Marta Vázquez Fernández, Pablo Álvarez Chaver, Flor Arenaza Gomorri, Ana Maria Bernabeu Tello, Natalia Bienzobas Montávez, Jose Guitián Bermejo</p> <p>West Country Region, UK: Giles Rickard, Nicola Rogers, Emily Widdecombe, Ada Myers, Iorwerth Watkins, Zoe Smith</p> <p>Gjøvik, Norway: Inger Katharina Gregersen, Pål Hector Maurice Godard, Trond Hulleberg</p>
Primary Contact and Email	Jan.cools@uantwerpen.be
Date Due	30 June 2025
Date Submitted	30 June 2025

File Name	TransformAr-WP6-D6.3- Catalogue of Solutions-v1
Status	Final version
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Suzie Durand
Suggested citation	Severijns, R. et al (2025). Catalogue of Solutions. TransformAr Deliverable 6.3, H2020 grant no. 101036683

© TransformAr Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except when indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorised if the source is acknowledged.

This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAr. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily represent the opinion of the European Union. Neither the CINEA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
LIST OF ACRONYMS	8
0.0 INTRODUCTION	9
1.0 CROWDSOURCING CITIZEN APPLICATION GJOVIK	11
1.1 Overview	11
1.2 Innovation details.....	11
1.3 Challenges and limitations	12
2.0 CHOICE EXPERIMENTS	13
2.1 Overview	13
2.2 Innovation details.....	14
2.3 Challenges and limitations	16
3.0 STORMWATER MONITORING/ MODULAR SYSTEM	16
3.1 Overview	16
3.2 Innovation details.....	17
3.3 Challenges and limitations	17
4.0 NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN LAPPEENRANTA	18
4.1 Overview	18
4.2 Innovation details.....	18
4.3 Challenges and limitations	19
5.0 NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN THE WEST COUNTRY REGION	20
5.1 Overview	20
5.2 Innovation details.....	21
5.3 Challenges and limitations	22
6.0 PAYMENT FOR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES	23
6.1 Overview	23
6.2 Innovation details.....	24
6.3 Challenges and limitations	26
7.0 LOCAL ADAPTATION FUND	26
7.1 Overview	26
7.2 Innovation details.....	27
7.3 Challenges and limitations	28
8.0 NUDGING SOLUTION	29
8.1 Overview	29
8.2 Innovation details.....	30
8.3 Challenges and limitations	31
9.0 MUSSEL-RAFT MONITORING.....	32
9.1 Overview	32

9.2 Innovation details.....	33
9.3 Challenges and limitations	36
10.0 INTERTIDAL MONITORING	36
10.1 Overview.....	36
10.2 Innovation details.....	37
10.3 Challenges and limitations.....	38
11.0 RESILIENCE INDEX.....	39
11.1 Overview.....	39
11.2 Innovation details.....	40
11.3 Challenges and limitations.....	41
12.0 INSURANCE SCHEMES	42
12.1 Overview.....	42
12.2 Innovation details.....	42
12.3 Challenges and limitations.....	43
13.0 SMART CLIMATE STATIONS	43
13.1 Overview.....	43
13.2 Innovation details.....	44
13.3 Challenges and limitations.....	45
14.0 CITIZEN APPLICATION EGALEO	46
14.1 Overview.....	46
14.2 Innovation details.....	46
14.3 Challenges and limitations.....	48
15.0 CLIMATE INNOVATION HUB	48
15.1 Overview.....	48
15.2 Innovation details.....	49
15.3 Challenges and limitations.....	49
16.0 STUDENTS AWARENESS RAISING	50
16.1 Overview.....	50
16.2 Innovation details.....	50
16.3 Challenges and limitations.....	51
17.0 DEMAND ANALYSIS FOR SOCIAL SERVICES AND INFRASTRUCTURE.....	52
17.1 Overview.....	52
17.2 Innovation details.....	52
17.3 Challenges and limitations.....	53
18.0 SMART GRID AND GATES	53
18.1 Overview.....	53
18.2 Innovation details.....	54
18.3 Challenges and limitations.....	56
19.0 COASTAL CONTRACTS	56
19.1 Overview.....	56

19.2 Innovation details.....	57
19.3 Challenges and limitations.....	59
20.0 CITIZEN APPLICATION LAPPEENRANTA.....	60
20.1 Overview.....	60
20.2 Innovation details.....	60
20.3 Challenges and limitations.....	61
21.0 CONCLUSION	62
21.1 Key features	62
21.2 Key challenges	62
21.3 Climate adaptation in Europe and future recommendations	63
21.4 Tools for transformational adaptation.....	64
References	65
APPENDIX.....	66
A.1 Description of Technological and Societal Readiness Levels	66

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides an overview of the adaptation solutions implemented within the Horizon2020-project TransformAr. 20 distinct solutions were implemented in 6 demonstrators and 1 replicator: Lappeenranta (Finland), West Country Region (UK), Guadeloupe (France), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Egaleo (Greece) and Gjøvik (Norway; replicator of Lappeenranta, Finland). The solutions can be divided into five categories: Nature-based solutions, Technological and digital solutions, Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, Governance schemes, and Insurance, financial and economics schemes. The solutions are equally distributed, with 4 solutions in each category. This deliverable provides a textual and visual description of each solution, also provided on the [Climate Innovation Window](#).

Through a co-innovation process, each demonstrator developed their own fitting solutions. For instance, in Lappeenranta (Finland), Gjøvik (Norway) and Egaleo (Greece), citizen apps were developed for awareness-raising and crowdsourcing. The West Country Region (UK) and Guadeloupe (France) identified the need for and studied more flexible funding schemes. Some demonstrators benefited more from technological solutions implemented in the natural environment. For instance, in Galicia (Spain), mussel-raft monitoring and intertidal monitoring solutions help to collect detailed data on oceanic activity to mitigate the consequences of potential climate change events. Governance schemes such as the coastal contracts in Oristano (Italy) and the resilience index in Galicia (Spain) lead to the governance that is needed for adaptation implementation. Nature-based solutions, such as those in the West Country Region (UK) and Lappeenranta (Finland) provide the most direct protection against future climate events, for example by absorbing more water.

After describing all 20 solutions, some key features or patterns within TransformAr's solutions are identified: the use of participatory approaches through stakeholder engagement, creating awareness and involving citizens (e.g., crowdsourcing), the collection of detailed data through innovative digital tools, and structural schemes such as insurance or governance schemes. In addition, key challenges arose around the topics of stakeholder involvement (e.g., difficult to maintain engagement), governance (the need for flexible governmental support), data availability (several solutions rely on the availability of high-quality data), and technical challenges (e.g., certain technological solutions may not yet withstand extreme weather events).

In the conclusion section, the deliverable is compared to a recent report of the European Environment Agency (2024), that summarizes the current state of climate adaptation action and the challenges and enabling conditions in urban Europe. The current types of adaptation solutions and key challenges largely align with TransformAr's findings. Some key recommendations by the European Environment Agency (2024) that TransformAr's solutions may have fallen short on include incorporating social justice and generating robust quantitative evidence. These are general difficulties within the climate adaptation realm, beyond the TransformAr project, that future projects and policymakers should take into account.

Throughout and apart from the solutions developed in TransformAr's demonstrators, several useful tools were developed that can support policy- and decision-makers to plan and implement transformational adaptation solutions. First, the [Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook](#) provides a guide to using co-innovation and involving stakeholders in the planning process. The [Climate Impacts Online Europe](#) tool can be used to gain a quick understanding of climate risks in European regions. The [Transformational Adaptation Scorecard](#) is a tool to measure how transformational one's plans or implemented solutions are. Finally, to evaluate the replicability of a certain solution, we refer to TransformAr's [Replicability Assessment Tool](#). A comprehensive overview of all tools and methods created and applied within TransformAr, per step of the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST), can be found on our [website](#) and in Deliverable 6.5 (*coming soon*).

LIST OF ACRONYMS

CMCC	Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Italy)
DCE	Discrete Choice Experiment
NBS	Nature-based solution
TA	Transformational Adaptation
RAST	Regional Adaptation Support Tool
NCSR	National Centre of Scientific Research Demokritos (Greece)
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust (UK)
MOE	Municipality of Egaleo (Greece)
LAPP	Municipality of Lappeenranta (Finland)
LUT	Lappeenranta University of Technology (Finland)
ADEME	Agence de la transition écologique (France)
CETMAR	Marine Technology Centre (Centro Tecnológico del Mar) (Spain)
UVIGO	University of Vigo (Spain)
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology

0.0 INTRODUCTION

Europe faces an increasing prevalence and risk of climate disasters like extreme weather events and floods. Short-term, incremental solutions are no longer sufficient. We need transformational adaptation, which refers to “actions aiming at adapting to climate change resulting in significant changes in structure or function that go beyond adjusting existing practices” (IPCC, 2022). In this light, TransformAr aims to demonstrate solutions and pathways deemed essential for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching transformational adaptation (TA). Solutions were designed through co-innovation processes and implemented in 6 demonstrator regions and 1 replicator region (henceforth “demonstrators”): Lappeenranta (Finland), West Country Region (UK), Guadeloupe (France), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Egaleo (Greece) and Gjøvik (Norway; replicator of Lappeenranta, Finland).

This report provides an overview and description of the 20 solutions implemented in TransformAr, see Table 0.1. The solutions can be divided into five categories: Nature-based solutions, Technological and digital solutions, Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, Governance schemes, and Insurance, financial and economics schemes.

Table 0.1 Overview of TransformAr’s implemented adaptation solutions

	Solution	Demonstrator/ Location	Type
1	Crowdsourcing Citizen application	Gjøvik, Norway	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
2	Choice Experiment in Lappeenranta and Gjøvik	Lappeenranta, Finland Gjøvik, Norway	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
3	Stormwater Monitoring / Modular system	Lappeenranta, Finland Gjøvik, Norway	Digital and technological solutions
4	Nature-Based Solutions in Lappeenranta	Lappeenranta, Finland	Nature-based solutions
5	Nature-Based Solutions in the West Country	West Country Region, UK	Nature-based solutions
6	Payment for ecosystem services	West Country Region, UK	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
7	Local adaptation fund (FLAG)	Guadeloupe, France	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
8	Nudging solution	Guadeloupe, France	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
9	Mussel-raft monitoring	Galicia, Spain	Digital and technological solutions
10	Intertidal monitoring	Galicia, Spain	Digital and technological solutions
11	Resilience Index	Galicia, Spain	Governance Schemes

12	Insurance schemes	All	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
13	Smart Climate Stations	Egaleo, Greece	Digital and technological solutions
14	Citizen application	Egaleo, Greece	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
15	Climate Innovation Hub	Egaleo, Greece	Governance schemes/ Awareness-raising and behavioural change
16	Students awareness raising	Egaleo, Greece	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
17	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructure	Egaleo, Greece	Governance schemes
18	Smart Grid and Gates	Oristano, Italy	Nature-based solutions
19	Coastal contracts	Oristano, Italy	Governance schemes
20	Citizen application	Lappeenranta, Finland	Awareness-raising and behavioural change

This report contains a description of one solution per chapter. The summaries provide general information on the benefits of the solution, the issues it aims to address, and the type of solution, and then go more into detail on the workings and development of the solution, its limitations and readiness for implementation. Depending on the type of innovation (technological or social), implementation readiness is judged by using the [Technological Readiness Level](#) (TRL) or Societal Readiness Level scales (SRL), following European guidelines Bruno et al. (2020). TRL and SRL represent the level of maturity a solution has reached, and hence how much development it still needs before it can be replicated and scaled up. The TRL was devised for rather technical solutions or inventions, and is about how ready a technology is to be used by a larger public. SRL is an adaptation of TRL that reflects the readiness of a solution to be implemented in society, which is more fit for non-technological solutions. An overview and description of the levels can be found in Appendix A.1. The solutions can also be found on the [Climate Innovation Window](#) platform.

1.0 CROWDSOURCING CITIZEN APPLICATION GJOVIK

1.1 Overview

Table 1.1 Overview of the Crowdsourcing Citizen Application solution

Solution owner/ creator	NTNU
Location	Gjøvik, Norway
Type	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
Summary	A citizen app for real-time flood detecting and reporting. This app allows residents to submit observations, including photos and locations, which are shared directly with municipal employees.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River floods • Pluvial floods • Heavy precipitation
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Models and tools • Education
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time integration of citizen data • Two-way communication between residents and municipality • Addressing flooding events better
Problems solved	The app leverages the combination of citizens' and the municipality's knowledge on floods and collects data to improve the mitigation and prevention of flooding events.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL7: The app is tested and has been used by over 500 users.
Social Readiness Level	SRL7: The app is tested and has been used by over 500 users.
Other resources	Learning stories on awareness-raising and behavioural solutions - Deliverable 4.1 Green Deal Call Projects Success Stories - Gjøvik's flood detection innovation

1.2 Innovation details

TransformAr focuses on enhancing urban climate resilience in Gjøvik, Norway, through innovative solutions for flood detection and emergency response.

The introduction of a citizen app for real-time flood reporting empowers residents to contribute observations, improving situational awareness for city officials. This scalable approach demonstrates how citizen engagement and data integration can strengthen urban climate adaptation strategies. Figure 1.1 displays the interface of the application

Figure 1.1 Interface of the application

The app integrates citizen data with sensor readings and other city inputs that monitor flooding, enabling a comprehensive view of flooding conditions in real-time. It also facilitates two-way communication, allowing the municipality to communicate directly with app users and share updates about flooding incidents and countermeasures. This innovative tool has improved emergency response prioritisation, reduced damage risks, and strengthened community participation in climate adaptation efforts. Within two months of its introduction and advertising over local media, the app gained significant traction, with over 500 uses and 100 citizen-submitted reports.

The citizen app introduced through the TransformAr project has significantly enhanced Gjøvik's ability to manage flooding events. Emergency and infrastructure services now benefit from real-time, crowd-sourced data, improving their situational awareness and response strategies. This proactive approach has reduced potential damage to property and ensured greater public safety during flooding incidents. Additionally, the app has strengthened communication between the municipality and its citizens, creating a shared sense of responsibility for climate adaptation. By empowering citizens to contribute to monitoring efforts, the project has also raised public awareness about the local impacts of climate change and the importance of collective action in addressing its challenges.

1.3 Challenges and limitations

Citizens use the platform to report problems other than flooding, such as road maintenance, littering and various other municipal issues. Instead of dismissing this, the citizen app could be adapted and used for a wider range of purposes. In addition, a potential challenge of such an app could be the continuous maintenance, as well as the need for ongoing engagement from citizens.

2.0 CHOICE EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Overview

Table 2.1 Overview of the Choice Experiments solution

Solution owner/ creator	LUT University, University of Antwerp (UA)
Location	Lappeenranta, Finland & Gjøvik, Norway
Type	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
Summary	A data-driven tool to uncover citizen preferences for green and grey stormwater solutions - empowering cities to drive private investment and climate adaptation through smarter, targeted flood risk policies.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy precipitation • Multi-hazards • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Models and tools
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unlock citizen engagement • Target flood risk reduction • Inform smarter investments
Problems solved	Our innovation tackles urban flooding - a growing climate risk that damages property, pollutes water, and endangers health. It reveals what drives citizens to invest in stormwater solutions, enabling people-powered flood resilience and guiding smarter, more targeted policy decision-making.
Technology Readiness Level	/
Social Readiness Level	SRL 5: The innovation has been tested in a real-world setting through surveys in Finland and Norway, validating the methodology and producing meaningful insights into citizens' preferences for stormwater management. While results are promising and relevant for policy, they have not yet been fully integrated into decision-making or formal policy discussions at the local levels. The innovation has demonstrated its potential and usefulness, but broader stakeholder engagement and institutional uptake are still in progress.
Other resources	<p>Learning stories on Insurance and financial solutions - Deliverable 4.5</p> <p>Other choice experiment within TransformAr: Deliverable 6.1</p>

2.2 Innovation details

Our innovation uses a discrete choice experiment (DCE) to understand which factors influence private citizens' willingness to invest in stormwater management (SWM) at the household level. By revealing preferences for green and grey infrastructure—such as flood protection, water quality improvement, maintenance frequency, and aesthetics—it enables policymakers to design targeted incentives and strategies that align with citizen priorities. The tool enhances urban climate adaptation by mobilizing private action, reducing flood risk, and improving water resilience.

The innovation is a behavioural survey built on discrete choice experiments (DCEs) (Figure 2.2), developed through a collaborative research process in Finland and Norway. It presents citizens with hypothetical SWM investment options varying in attributes such as cost, flood risk reduction, water quality, aesthetics, and maintenance demands. By analysing how respondents make trade-offs between these attributes, the tool quantifies willingness to pay (WTP) for specific features and identifies preference patterns across the population, which can be linked to specific solutions (Figure 2.1).

This approach makes it possible to detect both general trends and heterogeneous preferences within the community, helping policymakers understand what motivates or discourages household-level action. It bridges the gap between public goals and private decisions, offering guidance for designing subsidies, awareness campaigns, or regulatory measures that can accelerate the adoption of stormwater infrastructure.

It supports both green (nature-based) and grey (engineered) solutions and provides actionable insights for local water governance and climate adaptation planning.

Figure 2.1 Private Stormwater Management solutions

		<u>Definition</u>	<u>Levels to choose from</u>
	Reduced risk of damage to the house	By installing effective stormwater management measures on your property, you reduce the risk of flooding and minimise potential damage caused by excessive rainfall compared to what may occur in its present condition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less risk of damage - 50 % less risk of damage - 25 % less risk of damage No reduction in risk of damage (same as now)
	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Stormwater runoff is the water that flows over the surface when it rains or when snow and ice melt. Instead of soaking into the ground, this water runs off over streets, parking lots, and rooftops, picking up pollutants (like oil, chemicals, sediments and debris). Effective stormwater management will reduce the stormwater runoff from your property, including pollutants, flowing into local water bodies, thus ensuring local water quality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 75 % less run-off pollutants - 50 % less run-off pollutants - 25 % less run-off pollutants No reduction in run-off pollutants (same as now)
	Improved aesthetics of the property and community	The stormwater measure can beautify your property and the local community (or not).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes No (same as now)
	Frequency of maintenance required	The frequency at which you will have to take action to maintain the stormwater management measure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once every 2 months Once every 6 months Once a year Once every 2 years
	Price (investment cost)	The price to pay to install the stormwater management measure on your property.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 100 000 KR/10 000 EUR 40 000 KR/4 000 EUR 10 000 KR/1 000 EUR 5000 KR/500 EUR

	Reduced risk of damage to the house	Reduced stormwater run-off and pollution	Improvement of aesthetics of the property and community	Frequency of maintenance required	Price (investment cost)
A	 € 1000				
B	 € 500				
C	No new stormwater management measure				

Figure 2.2 Levels and attributes, and choice card of Discrete Choice Experiment

2.3 Challenges and limitations

- The effectiveness depends on high-quality, localized data and representative public participation in surveys.
- Results may not directly translate across cultural or geographic contexts without adaptation.
- It captures stated preferences, which may differ from actual behaviour unless paired with effective policy instruments.
- May be less effective in areas with low awareness of flood risk or where financial incentives are not feasible.

3.0 STORMWATER MONITORING/ MODULAR SYSTEM

3.1 Overview

Table 3.1 Overview of the Stormwater monitoring solution

Solution owner/ creator	LAPP, LUT University
Location	Lappeenranta, Finland
Type	Digital and technological solutions
Summary	Real-time monitoring of the stormwater system: flow rates and water quality to prevent pollution and manage runoff. The user interface is visual and browser-based, enabling access from smartphone or laptop.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy precipitation • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering and built environment • Models and tools • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality increased • Preparedness • Better monitoring
Problems solved	Collecting data to predict and manage flood events and stormwater pollution load. Growing urban areas require advanced water management solutions to handle increased runoff and pollution.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 8
Social Readiness Level	SRL 3
Other resources	Learning stories on Digital and Technological Solutions - Deliverable 4.4

3.2 Innovation details

The solution is a monitoring system with simple probes to monitor flow rates and water quality through individual modules. Real-time sensors in the manholes are measuring water quality, flow and volume within the water pipe and drainage system. Various indicators can be calculated from the data for authorities and study purposes. Images are provided in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Stormwater Monitoring in Lappeenranta, Finland

3.3 Challenges and limitations

Continuous maintenance is needed, and potential malfunctioning could impair data collection.

4.0 NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN LAPPEENRANTA

4.1 Overview

Table 4.1 Overview of the Nature-based solution in Lappeenranta

Solution owner/ creator	LAPP, LUT University
Location	Lappeenranta, Finland
Type	Nature-based Solutions
Summary	New integrative biofiltration area in the city centre as part of new urban adaptation standards, to reduce the amount of water led to storm water sewer systems, to filter harmful substances , and to filter stormwater into groundwater.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy precipitation • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering and built environment • Nature-based services • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved lake water quality • Decreased urban flooding • Improved urban biodiversity
Problems solved	There is an increasing demand for decentralized stormwater management solutions driven by urbanization, stricter environmental regulations, and public interest in sustainable practices. This demand is particularly notable in urban areas facing challenges from impervious surfaces and rising pollution levels. The a biofiltration area for urban runoff is addressed to municipal governments and urban planners due to its ability to manage stormwater sustainably in urban centres.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 7: The first pilot area is implemented and operating.
Social Readiness Level	/
Other resources	Learning stories in Nature-based Solutions - Deliverable 4.3

4.2 Innovation details

Water is led to the biofiltration area from street area. Water is infiltrated through the layers that filters the stormwater and reduces pollutants. The biofiltration system demonstrates the feasibility of decentralized nature-based stormwater management. It provides an efficient solution for filtering pollutants, while reducing the load on stormwater sewer systems. The system also acts as a flood buffer, redirecting and managing excess water during heavy rainfall events. An image of the biofiltration area is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Biofiltration area in Lappeenranta, Finland

4.3 Challenges and limitations

Currently, no challenges were highlighted.

5.0 NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN THE WEST COUNTRY REGION

5.1 Overview

Table 5.1 Overview of the Nature-based solution in the West Country Region

Solution owner/ creator	WRT
Location	West Country Region, UK
Type	Nature-based Solutions
Summary	Nature-based solutions are bespoke, scalable interventions designed to simulate natural processes for holistic environmental improvement. WRT implemented several nature-based solutions in the West Country Region, such as ponds, scrapes, swales, leaky dams, riparian woodland, and buffer strips
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Droughts • Heavy precipitation • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Governance and social innovations • Nature-based services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality increased • Fostering climate adaptation • Conservation of the biodiversity
Problems solved	Increasing rainfall intensity results in nutrient pollution entering watercourses from diffuse sources across agricultural landscapes. Loss of soil from landscapes reduces biodiversity, releases carbon, and reduces agricultural capacity. In rivers, nutrient-rich sediment causes harmful algal blooms, reducing oxygen availability particularly during low flows. This reduces riparian biodiversity, lowers resilience to global warming, and damages ecosystems and economies dependent on freshwater provision.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 9: Following the introduction of nutrient neutrality legislation, nature-based solutions for nutrient pollution mitigation are widely used the UK to offset the additional sewage burden occasioned by new housing development. As part of this, a wide variety of NbS are endorsed by regulatory authority Natural England as suitable for nutrient credit trading, provided baseline and post-intervention monitoring are sufficient to secure outcome delivery. This endorsement

	demonstrates high confidence in NbS as reliable technical solutions capable of delivering desired ecosystem services at scale. In addition, water company regulators recently introduced new regulations requiring 10% of water treatment to be achieved through use of NbS, once again demonstrating high confidence in these technical interventions to deliver robust outcomes.
Social Readiness Level	/
Other resources	Learning stories in Nature-based Solutions - Deliverable 4.3

5.2 Innovation details

Nature-based solutions for improving water quality include creating ponds, scrapes, swales, leaky dams, riparian woodland, and buffer strips (see Figure 5.1). These interventions help reduce nutrient pollution entering watercourses. Scrapes, ponds, and swales intercept or redirect nutrient-rich runoff into shallow depressions, allowing time for heavier particles carrying phosphates and nitrates to settle out. As water flows through a sequence of these features, excess nutrients are gradually deposited, resulting in cleaner water that can safely re-enter water bodies. The nutrient-laden sediment can later be collected and reused on-farm. Leaky dams, placed across water channels, slow water flow and promote the same sedimentation process. These dams trap nutrient-rich sediment, which can also be harvested and recycled. Buffer strips, consisting of vegetated areas between farmland and watercourses, slow down surface runoff, allowing nutrients to settle and be absorbed by plants. This natural filtration reduces nutrient pollution and helps protect downstream ecosystems. All these measures are cost-effective and environmentally sustainable.

Developing Nature-based Solutions (NbS) on privately owned land involves:

- 1. Ethical engagement with, and fair compensation for, landowners**

Practitioners seeking to introduce NbS into agricultural contexts must capably integrate advanced awareness of farm business in order to co-design interventions capable of adding value, or of mitigating impact and risk, for the landowner. Building trust and confidence with landowners is key to achieving positive working relationships, making third-sector organizations better placed to co-develop on-farm interventions than regulatory authorities. Compensation is determined case-by-case and contingent on NbS outcomes. Where within SSSIs, landowners may generate revenue through nutrient credits or reduce input costs via on-farm nutrient recycling.
- 2. Comprehensive design and feasibility assessments**

Understanding site-specific hydrology, historic land use, and climate projections is essential when selecting and designing NbS interventions. This ensures long-term viability and reduces risk. Where outcomes must be guaranteed (e.g., nutrient offsetting schemes), robust projections of environmental uplift (e.g., kg phosphate/ha/year) are essential for regulatory approval and planning.
- 3. Sustainable, low-impact construction practices**

Construction should use locally available, natural materials, and minimize habitat disruption, waste, and carbon emissions. Techniques should prioritize ecological sensitivity and long-term resilience.

4. **Comprehensive baseline and post-intervention monitoring**

Accurate, long-term data collection is vital to quantify impact, guide adaptive management, and verify outcomes for compliance or credit schemes.

5. **Ongoing maintenance and repair**

Routine upkeep is necessary to ensure continued performance, reduce failure risk, and maintain landowner confidence in NbS benefits

Figure 5.1 Nature-based solutions in West Country Region, UK. *Note.* Left: Scrapes and swales at Snowdon Hill Farm; Right: Leaky dams at Chubbs Farm.

5.3 Challenges and limitations

Limited political interest in environmental improvement reduces the availability of grant funding for sustainable farming practices and the introduction of NbS into farming systems. Unforeseeable climate impacts, such as changing weather patterns or new drought conditions, could threaten the performance of water management NbS. Lack of funding for ongoing maintenance reduces effectiveness over time.

6.0 PAYMENT FOR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

6.1 Overview

Table 6.1 Overview of the Payment for Ecosystem Services solution

Solution owner/ creator	WRT
Location	West Country Region, UK
Type	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
Summary	Lack of funding is a common issue when aiming to implement adaptation solutions, such as NbS. WRT studied the possibility for private-sector investment schemes to support Nature-based solutions through interviews and held workshops to identify models for green finance schemes. The scheme ‘Community Interest Company’ appeared to have the largest number of benefits.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Droughts • Heavy precipitation • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Models and tools • Nature-based services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality increased • Fostering climate adaptation • Obtaining funding
Problems solved	For organisations with little influence over policymaking, options for accelerating the flow of private capital into climate adaptation projects are limited. Investors may have certain requirements for viable projects (e.g. clear revenue flows, consistent rate of return over long time periods, etc), smaller companies may consider payment for discrete outcomes, such as reduced flood risk/increased drought resilience, as a viable investment. As such, alternative funding/finance mechanisms can be viable in the immediate term, prior to the widespread demand for ecosystem services emerging across the UK economy. In TransformAr’s Westcountry region (UK) demonstrator, a Systems Thinking approach was mobilized to map the organisational influence and potential of the Westcountry Rivers Trust (WRT). This led to broad strategic alignment with regional partners to accelerate climate adaptation into decision-making and investment frameworks within Devon and Cornwall.
Technology Readiness Level	/

Social Readiness Level	SRL3: The schemes have not been implemented or pilot-tested yet, but discussions and workshops with stakeholders took place.
Other resources	Learning stories on Insurance and financial solutions - Deliverable 4.5

6.2 Innovation details

To assess the extent to which Nature-based Solutions such as ponds, scrapes, leaky dams, and wetland restoration (see Section 5) currently present an investable proposition to private companies, Westcountry Rivers Trust (WRT) staff undertook a series of semi-structured interviews with relevant actors across the green finance sector. Participants in the bankability interviews identified 49 barriers currently preventing investment in Nature-based Solution implementation for climate adaptation, as well as 26 potential solutions. The barriers and solutions were divided into six key categories (public sector governance, private sector governance, economic, skills & knowledge, socio-cultural, and physical capital) and prioritised using a decision-support matrix based on the following weighted criteria: scale, complexity, and consensus.

Ultimately, research concluded that Nature-based Solutions do not currently represent a clear 14 Calls for Action to improve the viability of green finance schemes. Investment models operationalising blended finance in a non-profit model, such as a Community Interest Company or Special Purpose Vehicle are, however, considered likely to work successfully by the sector. This result highlights the importance of researching the bankability of nature-based solutions at the sub-national scale, as, whilst some barriers were consistent with international consensus, others were specific to the green finance context of the Westcountry region.

Investors usually focus on the UK’s urban centres, leaving the Westcountry with lower investment levels. The Southwest’s economy is worth about £81.6 billion (€97.1 billion), compared to London’s £562 billion (€669 billion). To attract traditional investors, ecosystem services – like carbon storage or water supply – must generate clear, reliable revenue streams. But the region, although highly dependent on these services for economic stability, has not yet established large-scale valuations. This lack of clear value makes banks and financial institutions hesitant to invest in expensive nature-based climate adaptation projects. However, individual companies at the local level often recognize their reliance on specific ecosystem services to keep their businesses running or to manage climate risks. These companies might invest smaller amounts, and if they pool their investments, they could finance large-scale nature-based solutions. Each company would then receive a share of the benefits, such as carbon credits or improved water supply, along with extra gains like enhanced reputation or better business performance. Interview participants supported this shared investment approach, as it limits the risk of companies exploiting the environment purely for profit.

To validate and expand upon the results of the bankability interviews, WRT held a Consultation Workshop with participants from the mining and minerals, renewable energy and infrastructure sectors. During the workshop, participants evaluated their dependency on different ecosystem services and reviewed hypothetical governance models for green finance schemes. Participants heard presentations on a variety of potential finance models, before evaluating these using scenario cards.

Figure 6.1 The funding scheme scenarios

Each model has multiple benefits and drawbacks, however, the Community Interest Company scenario had the largest number of benefits, including flexibility over accessing investment from a range of different companies, delivering value for communities, and having an inherently democratic governance system.

Following the workshop, all organisations in attendance expressed interest in hearing about future opportunities to implement Nature-based Solutions either to protect their assets from climate impacts and/or fulfil their Environmental Social Governance requirements. This is a highly valuable outcome, as not only does it open further avenues for possible project co-development and funding/finance, but it also creates opportunities to overcome broader barriers concerning siloing between the public and private sector identified in the bankability interviews. These results will help to accelerate investment in Nature-based Solutions for climate change adaptation in the Westcountry region.

6.3 Challenges and limitations

Key barriers identified throughout the interviews included:

1. Lack of decision-grade data proving the performance of Nature-based Solutions
2. The novelty of nature markets means investor confidence is low
3. Suspicion of green finance schemes in the farming sector
4. Poor understanding of demand outside of legislated markets (e.g., legally enforced nutrient offsets)
5. Disconnection between different sectors and industries divides efforts to create viable projects
6. Private profit models inherently lead to sub-optimal outcomes for nature
7. Lack of multi-value decision-making frameworks

7.0 LOCAL ADAPTATION FUND

7.1 Overview

Table 7.1 Overview of the Local Adaptation Fund solution

Solution owner/ creator	ADEME Guadeloupe
Location	Guadeloupe, France
Type	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
Summary	The Local Adaptation Fund (AF) is a blended finance tool boosting local climate adaptation in the agriculture and tourism sectors in Guadeloupe. It supports vulnerable groups and offers a replicable model for other climate change-exposed territories.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Models and tools • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports farmers with tailored climate adaptation solutions • Unlocks funding for adaptation by combining public and private resources • Strengthens local governance and enhances economic and community resilience
Problems solved	The innovation addresses climate change impacts on agriculture in Guadeloupe (droughts, floods, heat stress, soil erosion etc.) by supporting projects on water management, climate-resilient crops, agroforestry, and smart farming technologies. Its objective is to solve the funding gap for local, tailored adaptation solutions.

Technology Readiness Level	/
Social Readiness Level	SRL 7: Implemented in real-life conditions through six pilot projects in Guadeloupe. Received feedback. Stakeholders have actively contributed to the design and governance. However, the tourism sector has shown limited engagement and private sector financing has proven difficult.
Other resources	Video on TransformAr’s Local Adaptation Fund Learning stories on Insurance and financial solutions - Deliverable 4.5

7.2 Innovation details

The Local Adaptation Fund (AF) is an innovative climate finance mechanism tailored to Guadeloupe, a French outermost region. It is the first local fund in France fully dedicated to climate adaptation. AF specifically targets the agriculture and tourism sectors, two pillars of the island’s economy that are highly vulnerable to climate change. It addresses local adaptation needs through a regionally grounded, participatory model that ensures strong local ownership (Figure 7.1). By combining technical expertise, inclusive governance, and flexible financing tools, AF enhances both community and economic resilience. The fund acts as a catalyst, enabling local actors, small businesses, and public entities to access resources and implement impactful adaptation pilot projects. It also strengthens public-private collaboration, fosters long-term adaptation planning, and builds local capacity. Through its integrated approach, visibility, and strong engagement with stakeholders, AF has become a pioneering and replicable model for inclusive, locally driven climate finance, offering valuable lessons for other territories facing similar challenges.

Figure 7.1 Adaptation Fund Hybrid Governance Model

Developed specifically for Guadeloupe, the AF was designed to address the region’s most pressing climate risks – particularly in the agriculture and tourism sectors – through a participatory, territory-based approach. The AF was developed through an inclusive process involving over 30 interviews, surveys, and co-design workshops with local stakeholders, including public agencies, researchers, financial institutions, and community actors. This process led to the creation of a Technical and Financial

Committee made up of 22 partners (15 technical, 7 financial), ensuring broad expertise and legitimacy for project evaluation and selection. Figure 7.2 shows visuals of the stakeholder workshops.

The fund is structured around local priorities identified in a baseline vulnerability study. It finances pilot projects that demonstrate scalable solutions to challenges such as water scarcity, land degradation, and climate-resilient agriculture. Six initial projects were selected, representing a total investment of €1.24 million, including €989,204 mobilized through the AF and co-financing from public and private organizations.

Chosen after a thorough feasibility study, the AF's governance is designed to be flexible and adaptable to different financing strategies. Funders can choose between two modes of involvement: they may either delegate a funding envelope to the coordinating entity, which then oversees fund allocation and monitoring; or they can retain full control over their investment, independently assessing and financing the projects of their choice within the AF framework. This dual-option model allows partners to engage according to their internal procedures and capacities, while still contributing to a coherent, territory-wide adaptation strategy.

A dedicated coordination team supports project holders throughout the process, from proposal writing to implementation, ensuring accessibility and capacity-building. Public outreach events, like open days, have reinforced local visibility and trust in the mechanism. By aligning institutional innovation with on-the-ground action, AF not only enables concrete adaptation projects but also strengthens long-term governance and financing frameworks. Its success in Guadeloupe positions it as a replicable model for locally driven, inclusive climate finance across other territories.

Figure 7.2 Stakeholder workshops in Guadeloupe

7.3 Challenges and limitations

The AF faces several challenges, particularly in terms of governance and private sector involvement. One major limitation stems from the flexibility and hybrid nature of the governance structure. With multiple funders, each managing its own processes for financing, project approval, and contract signing, delays are inevitable at every stage – from project selection to fund disbursement. A more efficient approach could have been the creation of an autonomous fund with a shared pool of resources, where each organization directly contributes to a common fund. In this model, the coordinating entity would manage

the allocation of funds, sign a single contract for each project, and oversee implementation, significantly simplifying the process for beneficiaries. However, due to institutional constraints and time limitations, this model could not be implemented during the pilot phase. It remains a potential solution for future iterations of the fund.

In addition, engaging the private sector, particularly in agriculture, has proven difficult. Many banks are reluctant to invest in adaptation projects in agriculture, as they perceive the sector as high-risk and not easily “bankable.” This hesitance limits the private sector’s involvement and reduces the overall pool of available financing for adaptation efforts. These challenges underline the need for more streamlined governance and stronger private sector engagement to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of adaptation finance.

8.0 NUDGING SOLUTION

8.1 Overview

Table 8.1 Overview of the Nudging solution

Solution owner/ creator	ADEME Guadeloupe, Verhaert
Location	Guadeloupe, France
Type	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
Summary	Smart shower sensors and visual nudges motivate hotel guests in Guadeloupe to take shorter showers, saving water and reducing energy use – good for the environment and awareness.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Droughts
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Education
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water conservation • Energy savings and CO2 reduction • Awareness and behaviour change
Problems solved	<p>Our innovation aims to address excessive water and energy consumption in hotels caused by long showers, as well as the lack of awareness among tourists about their environmental impact.</p> <p>By encouraging behavior change through nudging (such as stickers, flyers, and feedback) and using smart shower sensors, the solution tackles both the direct consumption and the underlying lack of awareness about sustainable water use.</p>
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6 – 7: The innovation is between TRL 6 and TRL 7, leaning towards TRL 7 as the system is functioning in a real-world hotel setting. The next step (TRL 8) would be large-scale deployment with proven long-term effectiveness.

Social Readiness Level	SRL 7 – 8: The innovation has already received some level of social validation in a realistic environment. Advancing to SRL 7–8 would require broader acceptance, integration into policies or regular operations, and evidence of lasting behavioural change.
Other resources	Learning stories on awareness-raising and behavioural solutions - Deliverable 4.1

8.2 Innovation details

The innovation combines smart technology with behavioural nudging to promote water conservation among hotel guests (Figure 8.1). In participating hotels in Guadeloupe, digital shower sensors are installed to measure shower duration and water usage. These sensors collect real-time data, which is uploaded to a central platform (Aquadrio Hub) for analysis. Alongside the sensors, visual nudging materials—such as stickers, flyers, and feedback forms—are placed in bathrooms to raise awareness and subtly encourage guests to reduce their shower time. The experiment is conducted in phases: before and after introducing the nudges, to compare behaviour changes. Feedback is also gathered from hotel guests and managers through surveys and interviews, providing both quantitative and qualitative insights. This combination of data helps evaluate the effectiveness of the approach. The result is a measurable reduction in water and energy use, along with increased awareness about sustainable behaviour, benefiting both the environment and hotel operations.

The innovation was developed to promote sustainable water use in hotels by combining behavioural science with smart technology. The process began with the preparation phase, where researchers and project partners designed a nudging strategy tailored to hotel environments. This involved studying guest behaviour, identifying key decision moments (like showering), and developing engaging nudging materials such as flyers, stickers, and feedback tools to encourage shorter showers.

Simultaneously, digital shower sensors were selected and installed in hotel bathrooms. These sensors accurately track shower duration and water usage in real time. The data collected is automatically sent to a centralised platform called the Aquadrio Hub, which enables researchers to monitor trends and assess the impact of the nudging interventions.

The project was rolled out in three phases: preparation, a pilot experiment, and a full-scale experiment. The pilot phase helped test and refine the tools and messaging. In the full experiment, hotels implemented the complete nudging kit, and data was collected in two periods — before and after the nudges were introduced. This allowed for a direct comparison of behavioural changes.

To complement the quantitative data, qualitative feedback was gathered through surveys and interviews with both hotel guests and staff. These insights provided a deeper understanding of how the nudges were perceived and how they influenced behaviour.

The combined approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of what works in promoting sustainable practices. The results have already shown reductions in water use, which not only helps conserve a vital resource but also reduces the energy required for water heating — contributing to a smaller carbon footprint.

In summary, the innovation works by subtly guiding guest behaviour using nudges, while collecting detailed usage data via sensors — a powerful combination of psychology and technology designed for real-world impact.

Figure 8.1 Nudging for water conservation in Guadeloupe

8.3 Challenges and limitations

There are several limitations and conditions under which the innovation may be less effective or not work as intended:

Lack of guest engagement – If hotel guests ignore or do not notice the nudging materials (stickers, flyers, feedback forms), the behavioural prompts may have little to no effect.

Cultural differences – The effectiveness of nudging can vary across cultures. What works well in one country or demographic group may not resonate in another due to different attitudes toward sustainability or personal habits.

Technical issues with sensors – If the digital shower sensors malfunction, lose connectivity, or are installed improperly, accurate data collection and real-time monitoring can be compromised.

Short stays – In hotels where guests stay for only one or two nights, there may be limited time for nudging to influence behaviour meaningfully.

Lack of hotel staff involvement – If hotel staff are not engaged or supportive, implementation and maintenance of the system may suffer, reducing its effectiveness.

Privacy concerns – Some guests may feel uncomfortable with any form of monitoring, even if no personal data is collected, leading to resistance or negative feedback.

Over-saturation of messages – If guests feel overwhelmed by too many prompts, the nudging materials may be ignored or even become counterproductive.

These limitations highlight the importance of careful design, context-sensitive implementation, and continuous feedback and adaptation to ensure the innovation remains effective across different settings.

9.0 MUSSEL-RAFT MONITORING

9.1 Overview

Table 9.1 Overview of Mussel-raft Monitoring solution

Solution owner/ creator	CETMAR
Location	Galicia, Spain
Type	Digital and Technological Solutions
Summary	CETMAR leads the digitalization of mussel rafts to enable real-time environmental and production monitoring, tailored to stakeholders' needs. It gathers extensive data to optimize management in the face of climate challenges.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology • Services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine observation • Climate adaptation • Management (informed decision-making, raising awareness, and improving daily operations)
Problems solved	<p>Mussel-raft monitoring (MRM) addresses the need of understanding the effects of climate change on mussel aquaculture for enhancing resilience in the sector: extreme events and variations on oceanographical conditions (temperature, salinity, wind patterns, upwelling, pH...) pose serious challenges to the industry including disruptions to production cycles, management operations and infrastructure.</p> <p>To tackle these issues, MRM focuses on the design and deployment of an autonomous system tailored to the harsh marine environment. This system sensorizes mussel rafts using renewable energy, allowing for real-time, continuous monitoring of environmental and production parameters. By minimizing maintenance needs and enabling cost-effective operations, the solution is designed to be both sustainable and scalable.</p> <p>Beyond the technological innovation, the project aims to generate FAIR-compliant data, to improve scientific understanding of local ocean dynamics, support the development of early warning systems, and inform adaptive management strategies. This knowledge is critical for anticipating and mitigating the impacts of climate-related hazards.</p> <p>Socially, the project creates a direct line of communication with mussel producers to co-design solutions that reflect real operational needs, foster risk awareness, and promote sector</p>

	engagement and governance innovation. Through improved access to actionable data, the initiative empowers the sector to adapt proactively, enhancing its resilience and sustainability in the long term.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in operational environment (productive mussel raft).
Social Readiness Level	SRL 6: Solution demonstrated in relevant environment (productive mussel raft) and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders (5helix) to gain initial feedback on potential impact.
Other resources	Video of TransformAr Open Day: Climate Adaptation Solutions for Galicia’s Mussel and Clam Sectors Learning stories on Digital and Technological Solutions - Deliverable 4.4

9.2 Innovation details

Mussel-raft Monitoring (MRM) is a digital IoT solution tailored for marine environments, providing real-time environmental and production data to continuously monitor mussel raft behaviour over the long term. Installed on existing infrastructure and powered by solar energy, it autonomously collects and transmits data via telemetry, supporting operational decision-making and resource management. Integrated sensors capture structural and oceanographic parameters, offering insights into natural variability and extreme events. The MRM introduces a more agile, cost-effective, and low-maintenance approach to marine monitoring. The MRM is recognized by producers, regional authorities, and the scientific community as a valuable tool for testing adaptation strategies and enhancing resilience. While core components are affordable, oceanographic sensor costs may vary depending on required accuracy. Overall, the MRM fosters a shift in perception—monitoring becomes a key ally in the sustainable management of aquaculture systems. Images of MRM are depicted in Figure 9.1.

Figure 9.1 Mussel-raft monitoring in Galicia, Spain

Following the selection of mussel rafts, a co-design process is undertaken with raft owners to gather feedback and ensure their needs are met. Then, real-time monitoring requires the selection and installation of sensors to assess both structural and environmental conditions.

The system tracks raft movements, precise location, mussel ropes weight increase, and potential vandalism. A GPS device enables early warnings of mooring failure. A combination of gyroscope, accelerometer, and magnetometer detects displacement, rotation, orientation, and sudden changes. Load cells estimate mussel growth.

Meteorological and oceanographic parameters include air temperature, pressure, salinity, water transparency, and water column temperature—key for assessing marine heat waves, low salinity waves or changes in wind patterns.

At the same time, the monitoring hardware is designed and installed, and communication protocols for real-time data transmission developed (real-time version with telemetry). The main components include a Campbell CR1000X datalogger, a Vaisala WXT530 weather station, a Seabird Inductive CTD, a Seapoint turbidimeter, one main IMU node, and three sub-nodes (ULC) with the sensors that provide data on the conditions to which the raft is exposed, both structurally and environmentally.

Data collected by the datalogger is transmitted in real time via a Milesight UR32 router using a SIM card. Campbell Sci’s LoggerNet software allows remote connection to check system status, update programs, and configure the datalogger. The entire system is powered by photovoltaic panels.

Finally, data acquisition frequencies are optimized and managed through a data architecture developed in Django, an open-source web framework that integrates database management, user authentication, content administration, and task automation.

In the final stage, real-time data is displayed on a dashboard built with Grafana. This intuitive and user-friendly platform supports, visualization of the data and downloading time series data for both human users and machine applications. An example of data visualization is shown in Figure 9.2.

Figure 9.2 Data visualization of Mussel-raft Monitoring

9.3 Challenges and limitations

A set of minimum requirements must first be discussed and agreed upon with producers to address both their daily operational needs on the rafts and the associated scientific and technological objectives:

- The solution must integrate seamlessly into existing infrastructure without interfering with workers' daily activities.
- Technical and economic aspects, including potential impacts, must be considered during the design phase.
- Data access and visualization must be affordable for producers and support informed decision-making for more effective and sustainable resource management.
- Any future updates should be discussed with raft owners, leveraging their collaboration and practical experience.

Technological Requirements:

- The solution must withstand harsh marine conditions, minimizing maintenance needs while addressing challenges such as biofouling and corrosion from prolonged submersion in seawater.
 - Routine cleaning of equipment and solar panels, as well as water sampling for sensor calibration, should occur every 20–30 days. In more oligotrophic waters than those in Galicia, these maintenance intervals may be extended.
 - Maintenance scheduling may be challenging during certain seasons due to limited weather windows, making collaboration with raft owners essential.
 - Routine weighing of monitored ropes is required for load cell calibration.
 - Regular checks of wiring and M12 connectors are necessary to prevent corrosion.
- The system is designed to operate autonomously for data collection and energy, allowing minimal intervention. The installation must operate autonomously for at least 15 days.

10.0 INTERTIDAL MONITORING

10.1 Overview

Table 10.1 Overview of Intertidal Monitoring solution

Solution owner/ creator	UVIGO
Location	Galicia, Spain
Type	Digital and Technological Solutions
Summary	The development of a simple, low-cost methodology for obtaining substrate parameters from sandbanks. This methodology, proposed in cooperation with stakeholders, will allow for the acquisition of long data series, improving knowledge for decision-making.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River floods • Sea level rise • Storms
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature-based services • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long data series • Scientist-stakeholder network • Accessible methodology
Problems solved	The decline in the productivity of Galician shellfish harvesting sandbanks threatens the local economy and livelihoods, its causes remain unknown yet. While water monitoring is well established, sediment data is collected at low spatiotemporal resolution and lacks a standardized methodology. Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM) provides an accessible approach for substrate monitoring to support the generation of long-term databases, helping improve the management and sustainability of shellfish sandbanks.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6: The INTERM solution has been successfully tested in four intertidal shellfish sandbanks and is now in its final stage. Over the coming months, INTERM will share the laboratories procedures to the technical staff of shellfish guilds.
Social Readiness Level	/
Other resources	Learning stories on Digital and Technological Solutions - Deliverable 4.4

10.2 Innovation details

The Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM) solution offers a cost-effective and collaborative method for monitoring substrates in intertidal shellfish beds. Built on strong cooperation with shellfishers guilds, INTERM aims to develop a monitoring framework that reflects their needs and concerns. This approach not only enhances efficiency and practicality but also fosters stronger stakeholder engagement.

The initiative began with a series of meetings with the shellfishers' guilds of the Ría de Arousa, during which study areas were selected based on sedimentary, oceanographic, and shellfish productivity parameters. Key monitoring variables were also identified to generate valuable insights for the community. With the guilds' support, seasonal sediment sampling and topobathymetric surveys were conducted. For a visual depiction of activities, see Figure 10.1.

Topobathymetric changes over time were estimated, and data on grain size, sediment composition, and heavy metal content to assess pollution levels were obtained. These resulting data were subsequently shared with the guilds, who in turn contributed their own productivity records where available. This collaborative process has laid the foundation for developing historical data series—something previously unavailable for these shellfish beds.

Figure 10.1 Intertidal Monitoring in Galicia, Spain. *Note.* Top left: Discussion forum between scientists and guilds; bottom left: Sediment coring; Right: Topographic works by GPS.

10.3 Challenges and limitations

There are few limitations to the implementation of the proposed solution, since the effectiveness of the INTERM solution depends on:

- Establish clear and efficient communication among stakeholders: No matter who leads the implementation—be it technical teams from shellfishers guilds, public agencies, research institutions, or private companies—it is essential that the results are assessed through a collaborative process. Effective decision-making must incorporate the perspectives and priorities of all stakeholders
- Design a suitable methodology: The proposed methodology is simple and low cost, allowing part of the sampling to be carried out by the stakeholders themselves, which facilitates long-term data collection.

11.0 RESILIENCE INDEX

11.1 Overview

Table 11.1 Overview of Resilience Index solution

Solution owner/ creator	UVIGO
Location	Galicia, Spain
Type	Governance Schemes
Summary	The Resilience Index (RI) is a mathematical model that assesses the adaptive capacity of value chain operations to climate change. Its insights guide strategic decision-making and foster scalable solutions for risk management and sustainability.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Multi-hazards • Storms
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Models and tools
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comprehensive adaptation capacity assessment • Foster decision-making with strategic focus on adaptation • Scalable to other sectors and regions
Problems solved	<p>Climate hazards pose a significant threat to productivity, economic stability and community resilience. The RI addresses the challenge of taking strategic decisions to adapt value chain operations to climate change amid complexity and uncertainty. It helps to identify vulnerabilities, prioritise actions, and guide effective governance to reduce risks and strengthen long-term sustainability.</p> <p>The RI framework integrates diverse data sources, including historical climate data, climate projections and the potential of the existing resilience factors to contribute to adaptation. Therefore, this tool is used to assess the relationship between key climate scenarios, which have the potential to negatively impact the mussel sector's productivity, and the resilience factors available to mitigate negative effects.</p> <p>The insights from the RI provide a comprehensive overview of sector performance and highlight areas for potential enhancement. This information empowers decision-makers to identify vulnerabilities, prioritise actions, and allocate resources effectively. This comprehensive assessment of the sector's adaptive capacity makes the RI an essential tool, with high potential in a variety of sectors, for ensuring a value chain remains resilient and sustainable, especially in the absence of</p>

	strategic tools to adapt operations in the face of climate uncertainty.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 8: Fully developed, implemented and qualified through testing in operational environments.
Social Readiness Level	SRL 8: Fully integrated and applied by stakeholders in operational environments.
Other resources	Video of TransformAr Open Day: Climate Adaptation Solutions for Galicia’s Mussel and Clam Sectors Learning stories on Governance Schemes - Deliverable 4.2

11.2 Innovation details

The RI is a decision-support tool that evaluates the adaptive capacity of value chain operations to climate change. It integrates climate projections, operational processes, and expert input to assess how well a sector—such as mussel aquaculture—can respond to climate hazards. The tool is based on a formula that relates risk scenarios with resilience factors and calculates performance across five key dimensions: Governance, R&D, Risk Management, Collaboration, and Operational Environment. The result is a visual, easy-to-understand dashboard that identifies critical vulnerabilities and areas with the highest potential for improvement. This enables decision-makers to prioritise actions and allocate resources more efficiently to enhance resilience and sustainability.

The purpose of the RI is to assess the adaptative capacity of a sector’s value chain to climate change, offering practical support for governance and operational decision-making. It was developed through a participatory, science-based process that integrates expert knowledge, climate data, and insights from key stakeholders. The methodology is structured in three phases:

1. **Contextualization:** This phase begins with the identification of key production processes and relevant climate and oceanographic variables (e.g., air and sea temperature, rainfall, sea level, upwelling, acidification). Experts and stakeholders assess how these variables interact with operational processes to define risk scenarios. Twenty resilience factors, grouped into five dimensions—Governance, R&D, Risk Management, Collaboration, and Operational Environment—are also selected to reflect the sector's capacity to respond.
2. **Expert Consultation:** Through two sets of Delphi consultation, experts evaluate the level of impact of climate risks and the moderating effect of each resilience factor. Each factor is weighed up based on its relevance to the risk scenarios, establishing its contribution to overall resilience.
3. **Calculation and Output:** A mathematical formula aggregates the performance and weight of each resilience factor, generating a synthetic index. The result is displayed in a visual dashboard, showing performance levels and areas for improvement (Figure 11.1). This enables decision-makers to easily interpret results, identify critical gaps and prioritize strategic actions.

Figure 11.1 Summary of Resilience Index results for mussel aquaculture in Galicia, Spain

Originally applied to port operations, the RI has proven to be a flexible, scalable methodology that can be adapted to other regions and sectors such as mussel aquaculture. Its strength lies in transforming complex, multidimensional data into accessible, actionable insights that empower stakeholders to build long-term climate resilience. The RI not only supports climate adaptation decisions but also promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders.

The first complete application of the RI was carried out in a real-world port setting in northern Galicia (Port of Punta Langosteira), where the tool was not only piloted but integrated into governance and risk management practices, demonstrating full functionality and usability. Following this, the RI was adapted and successfully applied to the mussel aquaculture sector in the Ría de Arousa, where it was again validated through participatory processes involving stakeholders, climate and operational data, and strategic planning. In both cases, the RI generated actionable insights and supported informed decision-making on climate adaptation.

11.3 Challenges and limitations

The RI’s effectiveness depends on the availability and quality of input data. In regions with limited climate projections or sector-specific data, accuracy may be reduced. Additionally, stakeholder engagement is essential—without active participation from relevant actors, the tool may lack context-specific relevance. Finally, the model requires periodic updates to remain effective as climate risks evolve.

12.0 INSURANCE SCHEMES

12.1 Overview

Table 12.1 Overview of the Insurance Scheme solution

Solution owner/ creator	All demonstrators
Location	All
Type	Insurance schemes and financial solutions
Summary	Climate change increases the risk of being affected by natural disasters. As a result, dealing with the consequences requires major financial efforts to compensate for losses, and in this context, insurance has attracted much attention lately as a tool in climate risk management. In addition to financial compensation for losses after an extreme weather event, insurance can provide incentives to reduce risk, and potential investors often ask for insurance to save their investment.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance and social innovations • Services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial compensation for losses • Increased bankability • Provide incentives to reduce risk
Problems solved	Closing the insurance protection gap.
Technology Readiness Level	/
Social Readiness Level	SRL7: Single elements have been proven in different regional context, thus the system prototype worked in operational environment. Refinement of is needed and retesting in relevant environment with relevant stakeholders.
Other resources	Learning stories on Insurance and financial solutions - Deliverable 4.5

12.2 Innovation details

Two approaches were pursued and combined in order to obtain a well-founded and representative picture of the significance of insurance in the context of climate change and to learn lessons from previous experience: The first one is based on a questionnaire compiled in communication with the project partners in the demonstrators and partners experienced in empirical research. The second approach is to compare the results from the interviews with related literature to access the representativeness of the outcome and to ensure the correctness of the messages drawn.

Approach 1: The questionnaire was structured along main topics, for example about the role of insurance in the context of climate change in general, the necessary data availability and measures proven to be beneficial to increase the insurance cover against natural disasters. The questionnaire was translated,

where necessary, into local languages. To some part, the questionnaires were completed in the form of semi-structured interviews, while others were sent out and then completed by the respective experts and stakeholders. The interviewees were allowed to diverge to explore answers in more detail, when of interest and relevance for the goals of the interview. The later use of the results is in anonymized form, with no identification of the respondent or their organization beyond the sector and country of location. The total number of filled questionnaires is 14. However, the idea of this exercise is not to do empirical research, but to have the relevant information for the different regions in Europe, and in addition to have the view of the insurance sector.

Approach 2: The second approach is to compare the results from the interviews with related literature to access the representativeness of the outcome and to ensure the correctness of the messages drawn.

12.3 Challenges and limitations

The output of this solution within TransformAr was a document that helps to identify insurance gaps, but more work is needed to solve these gaps.

13.0 SMART CLIMATE STATIONS

13.1 Overview

Table 13.1 Overview of Smart Climate Stations solution

Solution owner/ creator	NCSR, MOE
Location	Egaleo, Greece
Type	Digital and technological solutions
Summary	MOE focused on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) around key areas of the city. The purpose of the SCSs is to gather real-time data regarding the micro-climate of the city, supporting the public administration office to ready the citizens in case of climate emergencies. After careful consideration and design, the key areas have been identifying and the SCSs began their operation registering Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure, CO ₂ (ppm), PM 2.5 /10 (ppm), Wind speed and Rainfall.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Heavy precipitation
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart microgrid of weather stations in urban environment • Feeding CAP (Citizen Application) solution to inform citizens of MOE • Provide data for evidence-based policymaking from MOE side

Problems addressed	Provide data for evidence-based policymaking.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6: The grid is installed and functioning for almost 1.5 years in real-world conditions.
Social Readiness Level	/
Other resources	Learning stories on Digital and Technological Solutions - Deliverable 4.4

13.2 Innovation details

The Smart Weather Stations employ high-precision sensors to continuously collect comprehensive meteorological data including temperature, humidity, wind measurements, atmospheric pressure, precipitation, UV radiation, and air quality. This information is transmitted in real-time through advanced wireless networks to central servers, making it instantly accessible to citizens via user-friendly mobile and web interfaces.

TransformAr's Smart Weather Stations represent cutting-edge technology for comprehensive climate monitoring. These autonomous systems collect and transmit meteorological data in real-time, providing MOE citizens with accurate environmental information.

Key Features and Capabilities

The smart weather stations integrate multiple high-precision sensors that monitor various meteorological parameters including temperature, humidity, wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric pressure, rainfall, solar radiation, and air quality. This comprehensive data collection occurs continuously without human intervention, ensuring reliable 24/7 monitoring. The sensors are shown in Figure 13.1. Figure 13.2 shows a measurement example.

Advanced Communication Technology

The stations utilize sophisticated wireless communication capabilities including GPRS, Wi-Fi, and 4G/5G networks to transmit collected data instantly to central servers. This connectivity enables real-time data access for users regardless of geographic location.

User-Friendly Interfaces

Data from the smart weather stations is accessible through intuitive platforms including:

- Mobile applications compatible with both Android and iOS devices (CAP)
- Web-based dashboards for desktop access
- Customizable alert systems for weather anomalies

The smart weather station network complements the CAP application launched in February 2025, now operational for nearly three months. Together, they form a comprehensive climate information ecosystem that not only distributes data but also engages citizens in climate resilience efforts.

The integration of IoT technology with meteorological monitoring creates a powerful tool for climate awareness and adaptation. By providing MOE citizens with objective, real-time environmental data, TransformAr's Smart Weather Stations empower communities to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions in response to changing climate conditions.

Figure 13.1 Smart Climate Station sensors in Egaleo, Greece

Figure 13.2 Smart Climate Station measurement example

13.3 Challenges and limitations

Position of stations to create a grid is not trivial and environmental conditions may affect continuous functions (e.g. birds).

14.0 CITIZEN APPLICATION EGALEO

14.1 Overview

Table 14.1 Overview of Egaleo’s Citizen App solution

Solution owner/ creator	MOE, NCSR D & Octagon
Location	Egaleo, Greece
Type	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
Summary	A mobile app for gathering and distributed information; (1) it will be used to crowdsource data about climate awareness of citizens of MOE via questionnaire, (2) to disseminate TransformAr’s MOE solution to the public and (3) to provide notifications for climate related events
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Heavy precipitation
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crowd-sourcing data • Disseminate solutions • Notifications for climate-related events
Problems addressed	MOE built a series of solutions that work together complementary towards climate awareness and adaptation of MOE and its citizens. MOE solutions comprise of data collection from various sources, analysis and post-processing of the data and feedback the outcomes to the citizens and promote climate awareness or utilize them for evidence informed climate adaptation policy suggestions at local municipality level.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 6: Available in Android and Apple stores for citizens to download.
Social Readiness Level	SRL 3: The app is still being tested in real-world conditions and feedback is being gathered.
Other resources	Learning stories on awareness-raising and behavioural solutions - Deliverable 4.1

14.2 Innovation details

The Citizen Engagement App is a cutting-edge digital tool launched by the TransformAr project on February 24, 2025. This innovative application was specifically designed to increase climate awareness and encourage public participation in Egaleo, Greece. Some images of the app are displayed in Figure 14.1.

Figure 14.1 Images of Egaleo’s Citizen Engagement App

The solution consists of more than 20 points of interest for MOE citizens based on TransformAr’s Smart Weather Stations installations. It provides the citizens with objective, real-time time and sufficient data alongside alerts. In addition, it gathers data via questionnaires for subjects related to climate change and resilience, and climate awareness.

CAP serves as a vital component of TransformAr's climate resilience strategy, enabling two-way communication between project administrators and local citizens. The application allows users to access real-time climate data collected from TransformAr's Smart Weather Stations network, providing objective and timely information about local environmental conditions.

Beyond passive information consumption, CAP actively engages citizens through questionnaires focused on climate change, resilience, and awareness. These surveys serve multiple important functions:

- Gathering feedback on existing and planned climate adaptation initiatives
- Assessing citizens' understanding of climate-related topics
- Measuring agreement levels on specific subjects or plans
- Collecting project ideas and suggestions from the community
- Tracking how public opinion on climate issues evolves over time

The application follows effective survey design techniques to ensure statistical reliability and validity, with clear questions and appropriate response options. This approach helps TransformAr inventory and shape climate change adaptations for long-lasting benefits while identifying further opportunities for citizen participation in climate adaptation activities.

Now approximately three months since its launch, the app represents a significant step forward in TransformAr's community engagement strategy, creating a platform where citizens can not only receive critical climate information but also actively contribute to local resilience planning through their feedback and insights.

14.3 Challenges and limitations

The largest challenges for a mobile application are continuous app maintenance and development. On top of that, the app will only have an influence of many individuals use it. Dissemination is therefore important.

15.0 CLIMATE INNOVATION HUB

15.1 Overview

Table 15.1 Overview of the Climate Innovation Hub solution

Solution owner/ creator	MOE
Location	Egaleo, Greece
Type	Governance schemes
Summary	A municipal hub combining climate data, permanent exhibitions, and citizen-driven events to enhance awareness, foster innovation, and co-design local adaptation strategies.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Heavy precipitation • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Governance and social innovations • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate awareness • Citizen participation • Innovation generation
Problems addressed	Egaleo faces multiple climate hazards—heatwaves, urban flash floods, and environmental degradation. The Climate Innovation Hub (CIH) responds by transforming an underutilized facility into a dynamic space where data, education, and community meet. It tackles misinformation, limited engagement, and poor access to climate knowledge, providing the tools and environment for informed action.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 7: CIH is operational, running real events and exhibitions with integrated data from SCS and the National Centre of Scientific Research Demokritos (NCSR).
Social Readiness Level	SRL 7: Citizens and students are already engaging with the CIH, contributing ideas and feedback during events like Open Green Day and Living Lab workshops.
Other resources	Learning stories on Governance Schemes - Deliverable 4.2

15.2 Innovation details

The Climate Innovation Hub is a hybrid space combining climate literacy, real-time data, and community engagement. Located in a municipal facility, it hosts a static exhibition on climate change and TransformAr’s actions in Egaleo, while displaying live climate data from the Smart Climate Stations (SCS). Through hackathons, educational events, and open data access, CIH fosters a new culture of climate resilience and participatory innovation.

As part of TransformAr, the Municipality of Egaleo converted a multipurpose building into a Climate Innovation Hub. This transformation included:

- A permanent exhibition highlighting climate change causes, local risks, and municipal adaptation efforts.
- A live data wall streaming environmental indicators from 21 Smart Climate Stations (e.g., temperature, PM 2.5, humidity, CO₂).
- An events programme with “Open Green Days,” climate hackathons, and school visits where students analyzed real-world data to design climate solutions. Such an event is displayed in Figure 15.1.

The CIH serves as both a data dissemination center and an engagement space. Citizens, students, SMEs, and civil society interact with municipal datasets to gain insights and co-develop adaptation ideas. Events such as the Hackathon and Living Labs increase data literacy and empower the local population to shape climate responses collaboratively.

CIH is not just a knowledge provider — it is a local innovation catalyst, offering transferable value to other cities aiming to link technology, policy, and people.

Figure 15.1 A Climate Innovation Hub event in Egaleo, Greece

15.3 Challenges and limitations

A Climate Innovation Hub requires sustained institutional commitment, data system upkeep, and community buy-in to remain impactful.

16.0 STUDENTS AWARENESS RAISING

16.1 Overview

Table 16.1 Overview of the Awareness-raising solution

Solution owner/ creator	MOE, Demokritos
Location	Egaleo, Greece
Type	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
Summary	A climate education module, empowering 13–15-year-old students to understand climate challenges, co-design adaptation solutions, and build civic capacity.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Heavy precipitation • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Governance and social innovations • Services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate education • Community empowerment • Early adaptation mindset
Problems addressed	Youth in urban areas like Egaleo face climate impacts but lack scientific understanding and civic tools to respond. The awareness-raising module (AWAR) addresses this by integrating hands-on climate learning into schools and building community-wide participation through Living Lab workshops.
Technology Readiness Level	/
Social Readiness Level	SRL 7: The modules have been implemented in real classroom settings and evaluated. Over 300 students have participated; activities are continuously improved based on feedback from schools and stakeholders.
Other resources	Learning stories on awareness-raising and behavioural solutions - Deliverable 4.1

16.2 Innovation details

The **Awareness-raising Modules (AWAR)** are 45-minute educational sessions integrated into school curricula for students aged 13–15. Developed by the National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos" in cooperation with local teachers, the modules explain climate change, its local impacts, and adaptation strategies. The modules combine classroom teaching with active participation in **Living Lab workshops**, where students, parents, teachers, and municipal stakeholders co-develop real adaptation solutions. Around 300 students have participated so far.

Hands-on learning is reinforced through:

- Real data analysis from Egaleo's Smart Climate Stations
- Group projects on local resilience
- Participation in events like **Open Green Day** and the **Climate Hackathon**, where students present their adaptation ideas using scientific reasoning

This approach strengthens environmental awareness and prepares the next generation of civic leaders.

"Pavements and open spaces in schools must be covered with materials that reduce the temperatures."

— **Andreas Rigatos**, Principal, 3rd Middle High School of Egaleo, Greece

Figure 16.1 Implementation of awareness-raising module in Greece

16.3 Challenges and limitations

The program's long-term success depends on curriculum integration, teacher training, and institutional commitment to climate literacy. Hence, there are several roadblocks that should be overcome to implement the awareness-raising module in the longer term.

17.0 DEMAND ANALYSIS FOR SOCIAL SERVICES AND INFRASTRUCTURE

17.1 Overview

Table 17.1 Overview of the Demand Analysis solution

Solution owner/ creator	MOE
Location	Egaleo, Greece
Type	Governance schemes
Summary	A resilience assessment – based on quantifiable metrics – of the social services considering future scenarios
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwaves • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering and built environment • Governance and social innovations
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health/ social infrastructure resilience • Climate impacts on social infrastructure • Better planning for vulnerable groups
Problems addressed	We want to assess the resilience of social infrastructure, considering the future change in demand for the social services. Address different climate scenarios on the impacts on social services. Assess climate adaptation options on social services and infrastructures.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 4: Pilot-tested but not implemented widely.
Social Readiness Level	/
Other resources	Learning story on Governance Schemes (Deliverable 4.2)

17.2 Innovation details

The solution is a web-based tool (Figure 17.1) that performs a resilience assessment of social infrastructures (SI) considering the different capacities against multi-hazard extremes. The capacities of the SI follow the properties of the resilience triangle – anticipation, absorption, coping, recovery, adaptation – capacities. Also, governance, financial and capacity building dimensions are included.

DSI is designed as user-driven questionnaires in simple drop-down menus. This information allows to a) create new assessment and b) retrieve old scenarios and assessments.

Afterwards, for each capacity introduced, a new page opens and a series of drop-down menus appear. For each question, the user inserts the information in the respective indicator category. After completion of the questionnaire, the outcomes are the individual Capacity Indices (e.g. for anticipation or absorption), and the Overall Resilience Index.

Figure 17.1 Screenshot of results in web-based tool.

17.3 Challenges and limitations

The innovation depends on the capacity of the responders to know their infrastructure and the way it operates.

18.0 SMART GRID AND GATES

18.1 Overview

Table 18.1 Overview of the Smart Grid and Gates solution

Solution owner/ creator	MEDSEA Foundation
Location	Oristano, Italy
Type	Nature-based solutions
Summary	Intelligent and remote-controlled sluice gate that opens automatically based on real-time data, enabling adaptive water flow regulation. Designed to protect ecosystems and support local fisheries, it enhances both environmental and economic resilience
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal floods • Droughts
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering and built environment • Models and tools • Technology

Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate adaptation • Water management • Biodiversity conservation
Problems addressed	The innovation addresses poor water circulation, flooding, and ecological degradation in coastal wetlands. Without proper flow management, wetlands face anoxia, sedimentation, and biodiversity loss, especially under increasing climate pressure.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 8: The gate has been installed as a functional prototype and integrated with real-time monitoring, tested under controlled and operational field conditions.
Social Readiness Level	SRL 6: Developed with active stakeholder engagement, particularly the local fishing community, and shared through public meetings. Further institutional integration is ongoing.
Other resources	Learning stories in Nature-based Solutions - Deliverable 4.3

18.2 Innovation details

Smart Gate is a solar-powered, stainless steel sluice gate operated by remote control. It is connected to a network of multiparameter sensors installed at two monitoring stations: one in San Giovanni Pond and one at the river mouth. These sensors monitor water quality and hydrometric parameters in real time, including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, turbidity, and redox potential. Based on predefined thresholds, the system automatically opens or closes to regulate water exchange between the brackish pond and the sea-influenced area. The goal is to improve water quality, prevent stagnation, and maintain ecological conditions suitable for biodiversity and fishery activities. The system checks sensor data hourly and includes a weekly maintenance cycle under normal conditions. The Smart Gate is designed for scalability and can be replicated across similar hydraulic structures, supporting climate adaptation strategies through better flood control and lagoon ecosystem management.

The Smart Gate (Figure 18.1) is a solar-powered, automated sluice with a hydraulic motor that regulates water exchange between San Giovanni Pond—characterized by brackish, salt-influenced waters—and the river mouth. It operates based on environmental and hydrometric data collected every 30 minutes from two multiparameter sensor stations.

Figure 18.1 Smart Gate in Oristano, Italy

These stations are installed on reinforced concrete plinths resting on the muddy seabed to ensure stability in strong winds and unstable terrain. Each includes a data logger with SIM for transmission and a solar panel for power. In the pond, a second sensor unit is installed a few meters from the main one, serving as a control to validate measurements and provide backup in case of malfunction. On the opposite side of the pond, a weather station and two additional level sensors have been installed to monitor marine-side water inflows and weather conditions. While not directly connected to gate operation, they provide essential context on environmental dynamics influencing the entire ecosystem. The different types of sensors and stations are displayed in Figure 18.2.

Figure 18.2 Sensors in Oristano, Italy. *Note.* From left to right: Multiparameter station, weather station, and hydrometer sensor.

Sensor data is processed via a remote platform that activates the gate automatically when thresholds are exceeded (e.g., flood risk, low oxygen, high temperature). A weekly open/close cycle is performed under normal conditions. The gate can also be operated manually or remotely in case of extreme weather forecasts.

The pilot project included key cost components:

- the smart gate and hydraulic motor (~ 78,000 €)
- providing and installing 3 monitoring stations (~ 58,000 €)
- the birdwatching hut with integrated solar panels (~74,000 €)
- data management and IT control platform (~ 18,000 €)
- technical support and designing the solution (~19,000 €)

These investments reflect the prototyping phase. The project identified strategies to reduce future costs, shorten implementation time, and improve performance.

The system is scalable and can be replicated across other gates using the same control infrastructure, supporting broader climate adaptation and lagoon management goals.

18.3 Challenges and limitations

The gate is not effective during extreme flood events where the embankment is overtopped. It is designed for everyday conditions and adaptive management rather than as a primary barrier during storm surges. Moreover, as this is a prototype project, until similar solutions are implemented more broadly along the embankment, the ecological improvements will remain localized and limited in scale.

19.0 COASTAL CONTRACTS

19.1 Overview

Table 19.1 Overview of the Coastal Contracts solution

Solution owner/ creator	MEDSEA Foundation
Location	Oristano, Italy
Type	Governance schemes
Summary	A voluntary, nature-based governance model uniting public and private stakeholders to manage wetlands sustainably and boost climate resilience, based on a structured Action Plan co-designed with local actors.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal floods • Multi-hazards
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Governance and social innovations • Nature-based services
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated management • Stakeholder engagement • Wetland monitoring
Problems addressed	The Coastal Contract addresses the fragmentation of wetland governance, climate-related threats (e.g., flooding, sea level rise), and degradation of biodiversity in Sardinia’s coastal

	wetlands. It aims to create a collaborative framework that improves water system health, mitigates risks to livelihoods and cultural heritage, and promotes sustainable development in vulnerable lagoon areas.
Technology Readiness Level	/
Social Readiness Level	SRL 8: The Coastal Contract has been formally signed by 14 public entities, representing municipalities and regional authorities involved in managing the Oristano wetland system. Over 40 participatory meetings have been conducted with a broad range of stakeholders—including fishermen, farmers, NGOs, and community groups—during the TransformAr project. This demonstrates high stakeholder buy-in, institutional commitment, and strong community engagement in co-designing and implementing shared solutions. The creation of the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO), as part of the Contract’s implementation, reinforces social readiness by reinforcing trust, transparency, and adaptive capacity through scientifically informed participation.
Other resources	Learning story on Governance Schemes (Deliverable 4.2)

19.2 Innovation details

The Coastal Contract (COAST) is a voluntary, multi-stakeholder governance tool for the integrated management of coastal wetlands in Sardinia (see region in Figure 19.1). It is based on a structured and collaboratively developed Action Plan, which defines around 50 actions co-designed with local stakeholders to enhance ecological quality, biodiversity, climate resilience, and sustainable development. Among these, the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO) is a flagship action, designed and implemented to ensure continuous scientific monitoring and to guide adaptive, evidence-based decisions.

Figure 19.1 Coastal Contracts target region on Sardinia, Italy

COAST is structured as a voluntary agreement that brings together municipalities, regional authorities, environmental agencies, civil society, and economic operators to co-develop and implement a shared Action Plan for the Oristano coastal wetland system.

The process began with participatory mapping of local challenges and stakeholder engagement to define common goals (see Figure 19.2), which were formalized in a Strategic Document and a Negotiated Programming Agreement. The Contract outlines over 50 actions grouped under seven thematic axes, addressing governance, water quality, biodiversity, cultural heritage, climate change adaptation, green economy and environmental education. These actions reflect shared priorities and foster cooperation across municipal and sectoral boundaries.

Figure 19.2 Stakeholder engagement in Oristano, Italy

Among the most impactful actions is the establishment of the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO), developed during the implementation phase of the Contract. The LWO functions as a scientific monitoring hub, providing continuous data to support adaptive and evidence-based decision-making. It enhances the integration of scientific knowledge into governance, enables stakeholders to assess ecosystem trends, and aligns interventions with both environmental needs and local priorities. It also plays a key role in promoting transparency, public awareness, and trust among participating communities.

The Contract further integrates relevant EU and international policy frameworks, including the Water Framework Directive, Floods Directive, and Ramsar Convention. Technological tools, such as smart monitoring systems and water flow regulation, contribute to improving ecological performance and resilience against sea level rise and flooding.

As a replicable model for wetland governance, COAST demonstrates how multi-level collaboration, science-based planning, and inclusive participation can enable effective conservation and climate adaptation across Mediterranean and European coastal regions.

19.3 Challenges and limitations

- Requires sustained stakeholder engagement and political commitment.
- Dependent on multi-source funding for implementation.
- Needs adaptation to local legal and administrative contexts if replicated elsewhere.

20.0 CITIZEN APPLICATION LAPPEENRANTA

20.1 Overview

Table 20.1 Overview of the Citizen Application (Lappeenranta) solution

Solution owner/ creator	LAPP
Location	Lappeenranta, Finland
Type	Awareness-raising and behavioural change
Summary	An application called CitySen.App to involve citizens in flood monitoring and awareness.
Climate hazards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frost • Heavy precipitation • Pluvial floods
Themes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Services • Technology
Main benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness-raising • Crowd-sensing • Community participation
Problems addressed	The citizen application addresses a critical gap in Europe's climate change adaptation framework by allowing citizen participation and digital technology to improve flood monitoring and response. The demand for such solutions is expected to grow as extreme flooding events become more frequent, making it an attractive tool for public agencies, private sector stakeholders, and local communities alike. There is an increasing emphasis on citizen engagement in climate adaptation strategies, aligning with EU directives to involve communities in disaster preparedness.
Technology Readiness Level	TRL 8: It has been developed, implemented and tested with real users in a relevant environment.
Social Readiness Level	SRL 3: The app is still being tested in real-world conditions and feedback is being gathered.
Other resources	Learning stories on awareness-raising and behavioural solutions - Deliverable 4.1

20.2 Innovation details

The objective is to raise awareness of climate change and enable feedback from citizens. The app is a progressive web application. The target audience are the citizens. Citizens can view the situation in storm water system: quantity and quality of storm water. Also, street works, air quality and weather information are distributed. Via CitySen.App citizens can participate in citizen science. Using an observation form

citizens can upload their own water sample data. Observations are visible to other users in the map. Figure 20.1 provides a sense of what the app looks like.

Figure 20.1 CitySen.App in Lappeenranta, Finland

20.3 Challenges and limitations

The largest challenges for a mobile application are continuous app maintenance and development. On top of that, the app will only have an influence of many individuals use it. Dissemination is therefore important.

21.0 CONCLUSION

This report provided an overview of the adaptation solutions implemented within the Horizon2020-project TransformAr. 20 distinct solutions were implemented in 6 demonstrators and 1 replicator: Lappeenranta (Finland), West Country Region (UK), Guadeloupe (France), Galicia (Spain), Oristano (Italy), Egaleo (Greece) and Gjøvik (Norway; replicator of Lappeenranta, Finland). The solutions can be divided into five categories: Nature-based solutions, Technological and digital solutions, Awareness-raising and behavioural change solutions, Governance schemes, and Insurance, financial and economics schemes. The solutions are equally distributed, with 4 solutions in each category. This deliverable provided a textual and visual description of each solution, also provided on the [Climate Innovation Window](#).

TransformAr's solutions were created through a co-innovation approach. Relevant stakeholders were brought together in workshops to identify the most important risks and relevant, but feasible, potential solutions. This approach is summarized in the [Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook](#), and can be applied in other settings. The co-innovation approach led to different, fitting solutions for each demonstrator. For instance, in some demonstrators, like Lappeenranta, Finland, it was more feasible to adapt environments to climate change (i.e., a nature-based solution), while in others, such as Galicia, Spain, it appeared more relevant to use digital tools to keep track of oceanic characteristics.

21.1 Key features

A recurring trend in the solution descriptions is TransformAr's participatory approaches. First, a specific objective of the TransformAr project is stakeholder engagement. Several sections highlight the involvement of stakeholders in the design and execution of the solution. For example, the local adaptation fund in Guadeloupe (France) was created with the help of stakeholder workshops, and the mussel-raft monitoring solution in Galicia (Spain) was co-designed with relevant field partners, such as raft owners. Second, a multitude of TransformAr's solutions focus on creating public awareness and involving citizens, such as the various mobile applications to inform and involve citizens in Lappeenranta (Finland), Egaleo (Greece), and Gjøvik (Norway). In addition, discrete choice experiments within TransformAr studied public acceptance of solutions, which can be vital to decision-making and implementation.

A second re-emerging feature is the collection of detailed data through modern digital tools, such as mussel-raft and intertidal monitoring in Galicia (Spain) and stormwater monitoring in Lappeenranta, Finland. The successful implementation of monitoring tools allows for detailed tracking of climate change consequences. These data can help local stakeholders in the field (e.g., in aquaculture) and decision-makers to adjust adaptation solutions to local needs, encourage efficiency, and prevent further issues. In addition, once such tools are developed, they are easily scalable to other regions.

Finally, the importance of structural schemes, such as financial, insurance or governance schemes should not be underestimated. Governmental support, and multi-stakeholder financing of solutions provide the solid basis needed for the implementation of adaptation solutions. TransformAr's solutions, such as the coastal contracts in Oristano (Italy) and the local adaptation fund in Guadeloupe (France) are some examples of successful schemes.

21.2 Key challenges

Several key challenges arose during the design and implementation of the adaptation solutions, which can be categorized into four main areas: stakeholder involvement, governance, technical challenges and data availability. Many solutions require stakeholder involvement. For example, the coastal contracts

solution requires the continued participation of stakeholders. Even rather technological solutions, such as the intertidal and mussel-raft monitoring solutions in Galicia (Spain) face the challenge of maintaining the crucial involvement of stakeholders (e.g., shellfishers and raft owners). The nudging solution in Guadeloupe would have benefited from more hotel staff and guest engagement. The educational solution (awareness-raising) in Greece required the training of teachers. Generally, stakeholders should be kept interested, but also not over-solicited.

Second, good governance can make a difference in the smoothness of implementation. For instance, the local adaptation fund in Guadeloupe faced difficulties due to the inflexibility of governance structures. For the student awareness-raising solution and the Climate Innovation Hub in Egaleo (Greece), institutional commitment is of high importance to keep the programs running. Logically, governance schemes, such as the coastal contracts, also require a high level of governmental commitment.

Third, several demonstrators highlighted the technical limitations. For instance, MEDSEA in Oristano (Italy) said that the smart gate solution is not effective during extreme storms, leading to floods. In a similar vein, it is unclear whether the smart climate stations in Egaleo (Greece) can withstand certain environmental features such as extreme weather events or animals. As was also highlighted in the description of the mussel-raft monitoring solution, maintenance of such technological solutions is of high importance. Especially for coastal solutions, which may be more easily corroded by the natural surroundings (i.e., sea water). Similarly, if the nudging solution's water sensors malfunction, it impairs the ability to collect data. While most technological and monitoring solutions within TransformAr (mussel-raft monitoring, intertidal monitoring, smart climate stations, smart gates, ...) are already tested and implemented, future improvements can help to avoid technical issues in the case of extreme weather events.

Finally, the success of multiple solutions depended on data availability. For example, the choice experiment solution to measure public acceptance requires high-quality, localized data to allow for relevant conclusions. Moreover, the effectiveness of the resilience index depends on the availability and quality of the input data. In municipalities or regions with limited climate projections or sector-specific data, accuracy of such a tool may be reduced. Finally, several monitoring solutions (mussel-raft monitoring, intertidal monitoring, the nudging solution, ...) are only successful if the data is properly collected, stored and preferably visualized. Hence, data plays an important role in the development and implementation of adaptation solutions.

21.3 Climate adaptation in Europe and future recommendations

A recent report of the European Environment Agency (2024) summarizes the current state of climate adaptation action and the challenges and enabling conditions in urban Europe. The solutions currently being implemented in Europe fall under five similar categories as the ones devised within TransformAr: Governance and institutional measures, Economic instruments and finance, Physical and technological measures, NBS and ecosystem-based approaches, and Knowledge and behavioural change. The report concludes that there are several key enablers for climate adaptation implementation: sustained political commitment, good governance, sharing of good practice and peer-learning, citizen engagement, effective use of knowledge and data, and sustained funding. These directly relate to the three main challenges or enablers summarized in Section 21.2: the first two encompass the governance category, citizen engagement is emphasized in the stakeholder approach, and the importance of data was also recognized within TransformAr. While the majority of demonstrators did not specifically mention funding issues, some technical solutions highlighted the lack of funding for maintenance and the coastal contracts and local adaptation fund solutions highlight the need for multi-sectoral funding efforts. Some key recommendations by the European Environment Agency (2024) that TransformAr's solutions may have

fallen short on include incorporating social justice and generating robust quantitative evidence for solutions. These are general difficulties within the climate adaptation realm, beyond the TransformAr project, that future projects and policymakers should take into account.

21.4 Tools for transformational adaptation

Throughout and apart from the solutions developed in TransformAr's demonstrators, several useful tools were developed that can support policy- and decision-makers to plan and implement transformational adaptation solutions. First, the [Adaptive Pathways Transformation Playbook](#) provides a guide to using co-innovation and involving stakeholders in the planning process. The [Climate Impacts Online Europe](#) tool can be used to gain a quick understanding of climate risks in European regions. The [Transformational Adaptation Scorecard](#) is a tool to measure how transformational one's plans or implemented solutions are. Finally, to evaluate the replicability of a certain solution, we refer to TransformAr's [Replicability Assessment Tool](#). A comprehensive overview of all tools and methods created and applied within TransformAr, per step of the Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST), can be found on our [website](#) and in Deliverable 6.5 (*coming soon*).

References

- Bruno, I., Lobo, G., Covino, B.V., Donarelli, A., Marchetti, V., Panni, A.S. and Molinari, F. 2020 Technology readiness revisited: a proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services, pp. 369-380.
- European Environment Agency 2024 Urban adaptation in Europe: what works?
- IPCC 2022 Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA.

APPENDIX

A.1 Description of Technological and Societal Readiness Levels

Table A.1 Technological Readiness Levels

Readiness level	Description
TRL1	Basic principles observed (e.g., previous examples or research)
TRL2	Concept formulated
TRL3	Design proof of concept
TRL4	Technology/solution validated in lab (testing in a hypothetical environment)
TRL5	Technology/solution validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL6	Technology/solution demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL7	Solution prototype demonstration in operational environment
TRL8	Solution complete and qualified
TRL9	Actual solution proven in operational environment (competitive and scalable)

Note. Sources: [Technology Readiness Levels - NASA](#) & Bruno et al. (2020)

Table A.2 Societal Readiness Levels

Readiness level	Description
SRL1	Identifying problem and identifying societal readiness
SRL2	Formulation of problem, proposed solution(s) and potential impact, expected societal readiness; identifying relevant stakeholders for the project
SRL3	Initial sharing and testing of proposed solution(s) together with relevant stakeholders
SRL4	Solution validated through pilot testing in controlled environment to substantiate proposed impact and societal readiness (limited group of society tests the solution or a similar initiative)
SRL5	Proposed solution(s) validated in real/relevant environments, and by relevant stakeholders in the area
SRL6	Solution(s) demonstrated in relevant environment and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain initial feedback on potential impact
SRL7	Refinement of the solution and, if needed, retesting in the relevant environment with relevant stakeholders
SRL8	Proposed solution(s) as well as a plan for societal adaptation complete and qualified
SRL9	Actual project solution(s) proven in relevant environment

Note. Sources: [Societal readiness levels - Innovation Fund Denmark](#) & Bruno et al. (2020)

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed. A set of 20 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

